

1 Genetic analyses for linear conformation traits in Pura Raza Español horses

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11
12 **Abstract**

13 A linear evaluation methodology was developed for the conformational data in the Pura
14 Raza Español horse (Andalusian horse). The final design included 31 linear traits (20
15 primary and 11 secondary). A total of 4,158 records from 2,512 horses were collected
16 during 2008 and 2011, and 876 horses with repeated records (a total of 2,522 records)
17 were included in the genetic evaluation. Genetic parameters were estimated using
18 REML methodology (in a linear animal model), and the age, animal's sex, geographic
19 region, and the combination of appraiser*event were included as fixed effects in the
20 model. The animal permanent environmental effect was also included as a random
21 effect, and the pedigree file traced back the relationships to include a total of 3,025
22 horses. After the repeatability and reproducibility of the system were evaluated,
23 according to our results, the appraisers used the whole scale and showed an adequate
24 level of repeatability (≥ 0.95), and the reproducibility of analyzed traits was over 0.90
25 for all traits. Despite the fact that the quality of the morphological evaluation can be

26 considered adequate, further training is recommendable for appraisers in order to
27 improve uniformity. Heritability values ranged from low to moderate, from 0.01 ± 0.004
28 (*angle of shoulder*) to 0.26 ± 0.021 (*head length*) for the primary traits; and from
29 0.04 ± 0.010 (*lateral hock angle*) to 0.14 ± 0.013 (*head-neck junction*) for the secondary
30 ones. Genetic correlations between traits were also obtained, which ranged from 0.92 to
31 0.00. These results must be taken into account in order to reduce the number of traits
32 routinely collected in this population.

33 **Keywords:** genetic parameters, genetic correlation, heritability, reproducibility, Spanish
34 Purebred Horse.

35 **Introduction**

36 It is generally considered that **conformation** is more important in **horse breeding** than
37 in other species (Preisinger et al., 1991), particularly in those breeds traditionally
38 selected for their morphological characteristics (breed quality), such as the Pura Raza
39 Español horse (PRE). Besides, conformation **defines** the limits for the range of
40 movement and function, and the ability of horses to perform (Mawdsley et al., 1996),
41 and it is suggested that it has a relevant impact on movement, performance, soundness
42 (Preisinger et al., 1991) and dressage ability (Barrey et al., 2002). Therefore, using
43 conformation traits might be a useful means of supporting **selection for performance**,
44 since performance traits have low heritabilities and can be measured only late in life
45 (Koenen et al., 1995). In fact, conformation has been proposed for its capacity as a
46 performance indicator with high heritabilities (Saastamoinen and Barrey, 2000).

47 **Visual conformation appraisal** of livestock is probably the oldest way of collecting
48 information for selection procedures (Janssens and Vandepitte, 2004). Traditionally,
49 conformation has been **scored subjectively**, with different aspects being rated on a
50 numerical scale in relation to an ideal value. Subjective evaluation has been defined as
51 judging through the use of a personal opinion or feeling as the ultimate criterion for
52 what is deemed good and correct (Magnusson, 1985; Mawdsley et al., 1996). This has
53 been the standard approach to the evaluation of conformation for breeding and beauty
54 according to the breed standard, currently used in the PRE population for mare and
55 stallion inspections and in horse-shows, respectively. However, this evaluation system
56 has been criticised because of the lack of agreement with functional potential (Sánchez
57 et al., 2012). Two important drawbacks were noted when assessing conformation
58 according to the breed standard: conformation was appraised in a global manner and the
59 judges' preferences (in relation to their conformation ideal) played an important role in

60 the final scores (Rustin et al., 2009), and therefore, the scores are a judgement and not a
61 “neutral” description. Consequently, it was deemed necessary to develop a new system
62 to provide more accurate and uniform evaluations to help breeding decisions (Foster et
63 al., 1989). This was first introduced in dairy cattle, and a **linear assessment of**
64 **conformation traits** has been applied to most livestock species.

65 The linear scoring system has been designed to evaluate individual traits on a linear
66 scale. Unlike the traditional approach, it does not rate an animal in relation to an ideal,
67 but rather describes where the animal lies between the biological extremes for a trait
68 (Mawdsley et al., 1996), including all the variability in the population (Samoré et al.,
69 1997). By assessing traits individually rather than in combination and by describing
70 rather than evaluating, this method may facilitate identification of differences between
71 individuals (Koenen et al., 1995).

72 Thompson et al. (1981, 1983) indicated several advantages of a linear scoring system
73 over a descriptive one: it records degree rather than desirability, the categories used
74 cover the biological range, traits are scored individually rather than in combination, a
75 wide range of numerical classes can be used, which allows for analyses on a continuous
76 scale, heritabilities for linear traits are comparable to or slightly higher than
77 corresponding traits scored in relation to an ideal, and linear scoring allows for the
78 interpretation of biological relationships between conformation traits.

79 The breeding program of PRE includes conformational (Gomez et al., 2009),
80 reproductive (Valera et al., 2006) and performance traits (Miro et al., 2006; Molina et
81 al., 2008; Valera et al., 2008), as the main selection criteria. A linear system has been
82 developed to collect suitable data for genetic evaluation of conformation traits.

83 The main aim of this study is to estimate the genetic parameters for the linear
84 conformation traits appraised in PRE horses and to analyze the quality of the

85 information obtained by the appraisers to ensure it is used appropriately for the genetic
86 evaluation of this breed.

87

88 **Material and Methods**

89 *Description of the database*

90 The **database** included a total of **4,158 conformation records** collected between **2008**
91 **and 2011**, at **51 official concentrations** PRE horses. They belonged to **2,512 adult**
92 **horses** (47.1% males and 52.9% females), aged 3 years old or more (average age:
93 **5.99±2.87 years**). There were 876 PRE horses with repeated measures in a total of
94 2,522 conformation records.

95 The system was based on the linear-type trait classification systems for horses which
96 have been proposed by several authors and have been partly introduced into breeding
97 schemes (Holmström et al., 1990; Preisinger et al., 1991; Van Bergen and Van
98 Arendonk, 1993; Koenen et al., 1995).

99 A total of **31 different traits** were evaluated (Table 1), **20 of which were primary**
100 **traits** (directly related with body measurements) and 11 of which were secondary traits
101 (not related with objective measurements). Traits were chosen for their economic
102 relevance, for their potential for improving performance (dressage), for their potential
103 for avoiding defects (mainly limb defects) and for the possibility of being evaluated
104 accurately by the appraisers.

105 The linear assessment was carried out by a total of **12 appraisers**, using a structured
106 score sheet. These appraisers had previously been trained and tested in order to select
107 those who had provided the most accurate ratings in the previous practical tests. In this
108 way, each appraiser evaluated an average of 346.5 records from an average of 209.3
109 different horses.

110 The appraisals used a scale of **9 classes**, in which the extremes represented the
111 biological extremes for each trait.

112

113 *Statistical and genetic model*

114 The **basic statistics** for each trait were performed using Statistica software 8.0 (Statsoft,
115 Inc., 2007).

116 For the genetic analyses, only animals with more than one conformation record were
117 used. **Pedigree information** for genetic evaluation was collected from the PRE horse
118 official stud-book. At least four generations of the horses on record were considered for
119 the pedigree file for the genetic evaluation, making a total of 3,025 animals. The **genetic**
120 **parameters** (heritability and genetic correlations) were estimated using a multi-trait (15
121 traits each) BLUP animal model (REML methodology), using VCE 6 software (Kovac
122 and Groeneveld, 2003).

123 $Y_{ijklmno} = Ag_i + Sex_j + Reg_k + App_l + a_m + pe_n + e_{ijklmno}$.

124 where:

125 $Y_{ijklmno}$ = score trait k, with Age i, with Sex j, geographic region k, appraised by the
126 appraiser l for animal m; Ag_i = the age group of the animal (i=9 classes: 3 years, 4
127 years, 5 years, 6 years, 7 years, 8 years, 9 years, 10-11 years, and >12 years); Sex_j = the
128 sex of the animal (j = male, female); Reg_k = geographical region where the animal was
129 born, in order to include the effect of the region and the management (k = 1,..., 48); App_l
130 = the combination appraiser*event, to include the effect of each appraiser for each
131 evaluation event (l=1,..., 61), included as a fixed effect; a_m = the random effect of the
132 animal (m = 1,...,3,025); pe_n = permanent environment of animal (n= 1, ..., 876) and
133 $e_{ijklmno}$ = the residual error effect.

134 The **evaluation of the system and the appraisers** was carried out using the following
135 parameters:

136 1. *Repeatability*: the probability of awarding the same rating for the same trait and the
137 same horse in two ratings by the same appraiser. It is estimated as:

$$138 \quad 1 - \frac{(\sum DAS)}{(NA * MR)}$$

139 where: DAS =differential of 2 appraisals given by the same appraiser for the same horse
140 in absolute values²; NA = Number of animals with scores; and MR = maximum range
141 of possible difference² (in this case, 8²).

142 This parameter was evaluated for only 9 appraisers, because they were the only ones for
143 whom we had the necessary data.

144 2. *Reproducibility*: the probability that two appraisers produced the same appraisal for
145 the same trait and the same horse. It is estimated as an intra-class correlation between
146 horses, measured by more than one appraiser.

147

148 ***Results and Discussion***

149 The descriptive statistics of the 31 linear traits analyzed in the PRE population are
150 shown in Table 1. Most of the traits had a **mean** close to 5 on the assessed population,
151 although some traits had a mean ranging from 3.0±0.02 (*commissure of lips*) to
152 7.1±0.02 (*length of leg*) for the primary traits; and from 3.9±0.01 (*hock from rear*) to
153 6.3±0.02 (*breed quality*) for the secondary ones.

154 In general, the coefficients of variation were high in this study (CV>10%), ranging from
155 12.9 % (*angle of shoulder*) to 42.4 % (*angle of croup*) for primary traits, and from 13.5
156 % (*frontal plane knee angle*) to 26.5 % (*head-neck junction*) for the secondary ones.
157 42% of the traits analyzed produced a CV between 10-20%, 39% of them between 20-
158 30%, and 19% of them over 30%. In general, therefore, there is an important phenotypic

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159 variation for the traits analyzed in this population, which could indicate a high genetic
160 variation and guarantees a sufficiently high selection response.

161 The **mode parameter** showed that the most common class used in this population
162 ranged from 2 to 7 in primary traits and from 4 to 7 in secondary ones. The **frequencies**
163 **of mode** showed how many animals were appraised in the most common class, with
164 *width of head* being the trait with the highest frequency of mode (3,085 repetitions,
165 74.19%), and the *angle of croup* the trait with the lowest frequency (688, 16.56%), both
166 of which are primary traits.

167 The **range** of classes used ranged between 5 and 8 classes, and 7 or more of the classes
168 used accounted for over 87% of the traits analyzed. The use of the full scale allows for
169 more accurate differentiation between horses, while capturing all the variation present in
170 the population analyzed. Nevertheless, it can sometimes produce difficulties, because of
171 the pre-selection of the animals included in the datasets (individuals with serious
172 morphological defects were not presented for the evaluations, and, therefore, a linear
173 type trait description has not been performed for them (Vostry et al., 2009)). As shown
174 by Breen (2009), linear methodology may be better for a subjective scoring system with
175 a fuller use of the scale than the traditional evaluation systems, by identifying
176 differences between the animals (Vostry et al., 2009). In the sample analyzed, the full
177 scale was used in 11 traits (*space between jaws, commissure of the lips, head-neck*
178 *junction, neck-body junction, height of withers, length of loin, angle of croup, ischium-*
179 *stifle distance, length of buttock, breed quality and harmony*) and only 1 trait (*width of*
180 *head*) having less than six classes used. Therefore, the use of the scale described here
181 may be considered suitable for the evaluation of PRE horses, and appraisers are able to
182 use it to distinguish most of the biological variability existing in the population.

183 However, the training and continuous evaluation of appraisers is very important to
184 achieve this goal (Janssens et al., 2004).

185

186 **Repeatability and reproducibility of the system and the appraisers**

187 The quality of the breeding evaluation depends on the data collected and, in the linear
188 methodology, it depends largely on the quality of the appraisers (Janssens et al., 2004).

189 The analysis of the appraisers' procedure provides essential information for the
190 development of the linear scoring system. In order to obtain suitable information for
191 breeding evaluation, it is essential that appraisers use the full range of possible classes
192 and their scores are reliable. In this study, the evaluation of appraisers was carried out
193 using two parameters: repeatability (Table 2) and reproducibility (Table 3).

194 The repeatability could partially be improved by practical and/or statistical
195 interventions, as in dairy cattle, where it is a common practice to train appraisers to be
196 as uniform as possible (Rustin et al., 2009). However, it appears to be difficult to use a
197 detailed scale properly, since appraisers tend to prefer certain categories (Van
198 Steenberghe, 1989). The estimates of repeatability of the system ranged between 0.61
199 and 1.00 (Table 2). However, eight of the nine appraisers had an acceptable average
200 repeatability value (≥ 0.95), except Appraiser 1, who obtained the minimum
201 repeatability value. It would be very interesting to control Appraiser 1, since the lowest
202 repeatability results were obtained in his evaluations.

203 The reproducibility of the traits is also very important, because it allows appraisers to
204 discern the small differences between classes within the biological scale of the
205 population. The 31 traits analyzed showed a high value of reproducibility (≥ 0.90), with
206 the *angle of croup* as the lowest value (0.89, Table 3). These values showed that the
207 scoring procedure in this breed is suitable. However, it is remarkable that the linear

208 traits with higher coefficients of variation (>30%) produced the lowest values of
209 reproducibility (between 0.89 and 0.96), which makes it highly recommendable to
210 evaluate the definition of the traits or differences in interpretation between appraisers.

211 Although the results obtained can be considered suitable, the testing and training of
212 appraisers should be continued in order to make assessments more consistent and
213 uniform (Janssens et al., 2004). In this way, these results imply that appraisers should be
214 trained using regular refresher courses (at least once a year) in order to ensure the
215 collection of suitable information for the breeding evaluation of the animals.

216

217 **Estimation of genetic parameters**

218 The reliable estimation of genetic parameters (heritability and correlations) is essential
219 to ensure that a breeding program is correctly carried out. The estimates of **heritability**
220 for the traits analysed, and comparison with the literature are shown in Table 4. These
221 ranged from low to moderate: from 0.01 ± 0.004 (*angle of shoulder*) to 0.26 ± 0.021 (*head*
222 *length*) for the primary traits; and from 0.04 ± 0.010 (*lateral hock angle*) to 0.14 ± 0.013
223 (*head-neck junction*) for the secondary ones. In general, they were slightly lower than
224 those reported in the reviewed literature for these kinds of traits in horses (Van Bergen
225 and Van Arendonk, 1993; Koenen et al., 1995; Samoré et al., 1997; Rustin et al., 2009;
226 Vostry et al., 2012) and similar to Jakubec et al., 2009. These values would permit an
227 efficient selection of most of the conformational characteristics in the PRE population.

228 In the head and neck region, heritability values ranged from 0.04 ± 0.001 (*neck-body*
229 *junction*) to 0.26 ± 0.021 (*head length*). Heritability obtained for *head-neck junction*
230 (0.14) and *length of neck* (0.16) was slightly lower than those shown in the reviewed
231 literature (Van Bergen and Van Arendonk, 1993; Koenen et al., 1995; Samoré et al.,
232 1997; Rustin et al., 2009) and similar to Jakubec et al. (2009).

233 In the body region, heritability values ranged from 0.10 ± 0.015 (*length of loins*) to
234 0.23 ± 0.002 (*width of chest*). The heritabilities for the *width of chest* (0.23 ± 0.018), the
235 *dorsal line* (0.12 ± 0.017) and the *length of loin* (0.10 ± 0.015) were also similar to those
236 reported by Jakubec et al. (2009) for the same traits in Old Kladrub horses, whereas the
237 heritability for the *length of back* (0.12 ± 0.014) was lower than that reported by Rustin et
238 al. (2009) in Belgian Warmblood horses. The *height of withers* in the PRE population
239 had a similar heritability value than that reported in Old Kladrub horses (Jakubec et al.,
240 2009) and Dutch Warmblood riding horses (Koenen et al., 1995), but a lower value than
241 that obtained in Belgian Warmblood horses (Rustin et al., 2009).

242 The heritability values ranged from 0.01 ± 0.004 (*angle of shoulder*) to 0.22 ± 0.023
243 (*cannon bone perimeter*) for the traits analyzed in the forelimb region, and from
244 0.04 ± 0.010 (*lateral hock angle*) to 0.19 ± 0.021 (*length of croup*) for the traits analyzed
245 in the hindlimb region.

246 The *angle of shoulder* (0.01 ± 0.004), *croup* (0.09 ± 0.015), and *length of croup*
247 (0.19 ± 0.021) showed heritabilities in the same range as those presented in the reviewed
248 literature (Van Bergen and Van Arendonk, 1993; Koenen et al., 1995; Samoré et al.,
249 1997; Jakubec et al., 2009; Rustin et al., 2009).

250 Finally, the general traits analyzed in the PRE population have shown heritabilities of
251 0.08 ± 0.019 for *harmony* and 0.12 ± 0.031 for *breed quality*.

252 Understanding the **relationships between morphological traits** is extremely useful in
253 animal breeding for determining the breeding criteria and the possible breeding
254 response of selection programmes. In previous papers, linear traits were evaluated
255 separately, grouped by anatomical regions. In this way, no correlations were obtained
256 between traits from different groups, resulting in a lack of information about possible

257 relationships between traits, and potentially indirect selection responses. This is why the
258 analysis of all traits jointly was recommended (Rustin et al., 2009).

259 In this study, the estimates of **phenotypic and genetic correlations** between the 31
260 traits analyzed (Table 5) were used to evidence these relationships. Generally, the
261 horses' body measurements tended to be significantly correlated between each other
262 (Magnusson, 1985, Anderson et al., 2005, Smith et al., 2006). **Genetic correlations**
263 were generally higher than phenotypic ones. A large number of significant correlations
264 ($p < 0.05$) were observed, both for the phenotypic (80%) and the genetic (63.1%)
265 correlations, although only 2.4% of the significant phenotypic correlations and 39.8% of
266 the significant genetic correlations were ≥ 0.50 .

267 The highest values were obtained among the general traits (0.92). In the traits of the
268 forelimb region, the most closely correlated traits, from a genetic point of view, were
269 *length of shoulder* (with genetic correlations of ≥ 0.70 for 11 different traits). 24.5% of
270 the significant phenotypic correlations and 31.6% of the significant genetic correlations
271 were negative. These values must be taken into account if a selection of traits is to be
272 made in order to reduce the number of analyzed variables in the official breeding
273 program of this breed and to set up a morphofunctional genetic index.

274 High genetic correlations (≥ 0.90) were obtained between *breed quality* and *harmony*
275 (0.92), as was expected, because a good muscular system and well-defined proportions
276 are associated with correct leg stances and good movements (Schroderus and Ojala,
277 2010); *length of leg* and *length of forearm* (0.91); and between *ischium-stifle distance*
278 and *length of croup* (0.90), since the PRE has shown close correlations between the
279 body lengths. Although shape is very important for breed quality, Cervantes et al.
280 (2009) conclude that size is more important than shape for morphofunctional
281 characteristics in horses. When a high correlation between two traits exists, from a

282 genetic point of view, little new information will be added by appraising the second
283 trait. As a result, these results must be taken into account in order to reduce the number
284 of traits and to include in future genetic index traits related to functionality (mainly
285 dressage).

286

287 ***Conclusion***

288 The genetic parameters obtained in this study indicate that the linear scoring system is
289 able to generate quality information on distinguishable conformation traits in the PRE
290 population. The scale used presents sufficient variability to represent the whole
291 biological variation in the population. The linear appraisers are generally repeatable,
292 and the 31 analyzed traits are reproducible. However, even if the current data of
293 appraiser and traits seem adequate, training the appraisers would improve uniformity,
294 and is therefore highly recommendable. Due to their close genetic relation ($r_g > 0.90$)
295 some strong correlated traits such as *length of leg* and *length of forearm* could be
296 represented by a single trait. The magnitudes of heritabilities and genetic correlations
297 indicate that selection is feasible and horse conformation traits could be improved with
298 a suitable selection program based on the EBVs obtained for the different traits.

299

300 ***Acknowledgments***

301 The authors wish to thank the National Association of Pura Raza Español Horse
302 Breeders (ANCCE) for providing the data used in this study.

303

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428 Table 1. Statistical descriptions of the 31 linear type traits analyzed in the Pura Raza
 429 Español horse population (4,158 records from 2,512 horses)

	Trait	Type	Class 1	Class 9	Mean±s.e.	Mode	Freq.	Range	C.V. (%)
1	Head length	Prim	<50	≥71	5.3±0.02	5	1671	2-9	19.3
2	Width of head	Prim	≤17	≥39	3.3±0.01	3	3085	2-7	18.0
3	Space between jaws	Prim	<4	≥12	3.5±0.02	3	1737	1-9	35.3
4	Commissure of lips	Prim	≤7	≥15	3.1±0.02	2	1449	1-9	41.0
5	Head-neck junction	Sec	Very impasted	Very marked	5.0±0.02	5	1122	1-9	26.5
6	Upper neck line	Sec	Very thin	Very thick	5.6±0.02	6	1170	2-9	22.6
7	Length of neck	Prim	<62	≥84	5.8±0.02	6	1304	1-8	24.7
8	Neck-body junction	Prim	<2	≥23	3.7±0.02	4	1566	1-9	31.4
9	Width of chest	Prim	≤20	≥42	4.9±0.02	5	1437	2-9	23.3
10	Height of withers	Prim	<3	≥11	5.9±0.03	7	1157	1-9	27.0
11	Length of back	Prim	≤25	≥40	5.2±0.01	5	1948	2-9	17.2
12	Length of loin	Prim	<20	≥34	6.2±0.02	7	1816	1-9	16.5
13	Dorsal line	Sec	Convex	Very concave	5.0±0.02	5	1633	1-8	22.2
14	Length of shoulder	Prim	<59	≥73	5.4±0.03	4	1074	2-9	30.5
15	Angle of shoulder	Prim	<35	≥57	7.0±0.01	7	2254	2-9	12.9
16	Length of forearm	Prim	<36	≥50	6.5±0.02	7	2280	2-9	15.6
17	Lateral angle of knee	Sec	Very buck-kneed	Very calf-kneed	5.1±0.01	5	2492	1-8	14.4
18	Frontal angle of knee	Sec	Very closed	Very open	5.3±0.01	5	2305	2-8	13.5
19	Cannon bone perimeter	Prim	≤16	≥24	5.3±0.02	5	1470	2-9	21.3
20	Length of croup	Prim	<40	≥61	6.4±0.02	7	1680	2-9	14.8
21	Angle of croup	Prim	<5	≥29	4.8±0.03	7	688	1-9	42.4
22	Point of hip-stifle distance	Prim	<40	≥61	3.7±0.02	3	2346	1-8	30.8
23	Ischium-stifle distance	Prim	<47	≥61	4.4±0.02	5	1783	1-9	22.1
24	Length of buttock	Prim	<35	≥55	5.8±0.02	6	1691	1-9	17.2
25	Length of leg	Prim	<40	≥60	7.1±0.02	7	1424	3-9	18.4
26	Muscular development	Sec	Very scarce	Very developed	5.5±0.02	6	1426	2-9	20.3
27	Rear tendon development	Sec	Very thin	Very developed	5.0±0.02	5	1919	2-9	19.6
28	Hock from rear	Sec	Very convergent	Very divergent	4.0±0.01	4	2094	1-7	19.2
29	Lateral hock angle	Sec	Very closed	Very open	4.8±0.02	5	1620	2-9	21.6
30	Breed quality	Sec	Not true to type	True to type	6.3±0.02	7	1817	1-9	21.5
31	Harmony	Sec	Not harmonious	Very harmonious	5.7±0.02	5	1724	1-9	22.7

430 All lengths are shown in cm and all angles are shown in degrees. Prim= Primary trait, Sec= Secondary trait, Freq= Number of
 431 repetitions of the Mode, Class 1= lowest biological class, Class 9= highest biological class.

432

433 Table 2. Repeatability values for 9 appraisers who assessed repeated horses in the linear
 434 scoring system across the 31 traits evaluated in the PRE population.
 435

Trait	Appraisers								
	1	3	4	5	6	9	10	11	12
1	0.938	0.998	0.992	0.953	0.990	0.977	0.996	0.985	0.984
2	0.965	1.000	0.992	0.998	1.000	0.985	0.997	0.997	0.938
3	0.859	0.998	0.992	0.936	0.979	0.973	1.000	0.977	1.000
4	0.965	0.990	0.992	0.941	0.984	0.967	0.993	0.975	0.938
5	0.965	0.957	0.993	0.969	0.974	0.956	0.978	0.963	0.859
6	1.000	0.978	0.992	0.948	0.990	0.990	0.970	0.978	0.938
7	0.938	0.987	0.992	0.957	0.969	0.972	0.992	0.972	0.859
8	0.965	0.985	0.992	0.962	0.990	0.958	0.993	0.973	0.984
9	0.902	0.993	0.992	0.988	0.995	0.978	0.995	0.985	0.984
10	0.965	0.992	0.992	0.965	0.990	0.965	0.989	0.976	0.859
11	0.984	0.999	0.992	0.984	0.979	0.982	0.998	0.993	0.984
12	0.996	0.994	0.992	0.951	0.995	0.975	0.995	0.988	1.000
13	0.996	0.974	0.992	0.960	0.974	0.982	0.985	0.981	0.859
14	0.609	0.997	0.992	0.937	0.958	0.958	0.996	0.985	0.938
15	0.996	0.982	0.992	0.951	0.984	0.977	0.996	0.987	1.000
16	0.984	1.000	0.992	0.954	0.979	0.977	0.984	0.985	0.938
17	0.984	0.991	0.992	0.992	0.995	0.994	0.982	0.996	1.000
18	0.995	0.984	0.992	0.996	0.995	0.979	0.981	0.994	1.000
19	0.984	0.990	0.992	0.988	0.995	0.986	0.990	0.978	0.984
20	0.984	0.999	0.992	0.963	0.990	0.985	0.994	0.985	1.000
21	0.984	0.993	0.992	0.967	0.953	0.931	0.992	0.962	1.000
22	0.965	0.998	0.992	0.979	0.984	0.969	0.996	0.995	0.984
23	0.902	1.000	0.992	0.967	0.995	0.973	0.997	0.994	0.859
24	0.996	0.985	0.992	0.933	0.995	0.975	0.992	0.974	0.984
25	0.984	0.994	0.992	0.902	0.984	0.970	0.995	0.967	0.984
26	0.984	0.962	0.992	0.953	0.969	0.979	0.983	0.980	1.000
27	0.996	0.986	0.992	0.981	0.974	0.983	0.991	0.976	1.000
28	0.984	0.986	0.992	0.985	0.995	0.978	0.994	0.989	1.000
29	0.996	0.989	0.992	0.967	0.990	0.977	0.994	0.981	0.984
30	0.984	0.954	0.993	0.980	0.979	0.944	0.985	0.997	0.984
31	0.965	0.967	0.992	0.976	0.990	0.911	0.982	0.998	0.984
Average	0.954	0.987	0.985	0.964	0.984	0.971	0.990	0.983	0.962
Maximum	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.998	1.000	0.994	1.000	0.998	1.000
Minimum	0.609	0.954	0.961	0.902	0.953	0.911	0.970	0.962	0.859

Correspondence of number of traits are shown in Table 1.

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439 Table 3. Reproducibility values for 31 traits included in the linear scoring system of the
440 Pura Raza Español horse population.

441

Trait	Reproducibility
Head length	0.97
Width of head	0.99
Space between jaws	0.95
Commissure of the lips	0.95
Head-neck junction	0.96
Upper neck line	0.97
Length of neck	0.95
Neck-body junction	0.97
Width of chest	0.97
Height of withers	0.93
Length of back	0.98
Length of loin	0.97
Dorsal line	0.97
Length of shoulder	0.92
Angle of shoulder	0.98
Length of forearm	0.97
Lateral angle of knee	0.99
Frontal angle of knee	0.99
Cannon bone perimeter	0.98
Length of croup	0.98
Angle of croup	0.89
Point of hip-stifle distance	0.96
Ischium-stifle distance	0.97
Length of buttock	0.98
Length of leg	0.95
Muscular development	0.97
Rear tendon development	0.97
Hock from rear	0.98
Lateral hock angle	0.97
Breed quality	0.95
Harmony	0.95

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446 Table 4. Comparison with other breeds of the heritability estimated in Pura Raza Español (PRE) horses
 447 for the 31 linear traits.
 448

Trait	PRE	SP ¹	DWRH ²	H ³	OKH ⁴	BWH ⁵
Head length	0.26					
Width of head	0.08					
Space between jaws	0.13					
Commissure of lips	0.09					
Head-neck junction	0.14		0.21	0.24	0.12	0.26
Upper neck line	0.12				0.16	
Length of neck	0.16	0.31	0.21	0.24	0.12	0.27
Neck-body junction	0.04			0.15		
Width of chest	0.23	0.18			0.13	
Height of withers	0.19		0.19		0.17	0.34
Length of back	0.12		0.18			0.34
Length of loin	0.10		0.18		0.14	
Dorsal line	0.12		0.16		0.12	
Length of shoulder	0.19	0.27	0.16	0.15	0.05	0.31
Angle of shoulder	0.01	0.26		0.09	0.01	
Length of forearm	0.10			0.05		
Lateral angle of knee	0.09					
Frontal angle of knee	0.07					
Cannon bone perimeter	0.22				0.28	
Length of croup	0.19	0.21	0.15	0.23	0.06	0.30
Angle of croup	0.09	0.10		0.09		0.30
Point of hip-stifle distance	0.10					
Ischium-stifle distance	0.09					
Length of buttock	0.13					
Length of leg	0.17					
Muscular development	0.12		0.16			
Rear tendon development	0.12					
Hock from rear	0.05			0.10		
Lateral hock angle	0.04			0.16		
Breed quality	0.12					
Harmony	0.08					

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¹. SP= Shetland Pony (Van Bergen et al 1993);
² DWRH= Dutch Warmblood Riding Horse (Koenen et al 1995);
³ H = Halfinger horse (Samore et al 1997);
⁴. OKH =Old Kladrub horse (Jakubec et al. 2009);
⁵. BWH = Belgian Warmblood horse (Rustin et al 2009).

455 Table 5. Heritability values (diagonal), genetic (above the diagonal) and phenotypic
 456 correlations (below the diagonal) between the 31 linear type traits analyzed in the Pura
 457 Raza Español horse.
 458

Trait	Head and neck								Body					Forelimb					Hindlimb									General			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
1	3	4	0	5	-1	8	7	2	3	2	5	6	-3	7	6	8	-2	2	7	8	-3	8	8	8	9	4	9	4	-4	7	6
2	-0	1	2	5	-6	6	1	1	4	2	3	5	0	4	3	6	2	2	7	5	-3	4	2	3	4	-6	5	2	3	-2	-2
3	4	-1	2	-2	5	-2	3	-2	1	4	-4	-3	-1	-1	-1	4	-6	1	2	4	-5	1	1	-1	-1	-1	2	4	-1	-1	4
4	4	2	6	1	-2	4	3	-4	5	2	1	3	4	1	-1	4	-3	-1	4	4	-7	3	3	4	2	-4	2	-3	-6	2	-3
5	3	-2	3	1	3	-3	3	2	1	-2	-4	-2	3	-1	-4	1	-8	-5	-2	-1	-1	1	2	-2	-3	3	1	3	-1	4	4
6	3	1	2	2	-1	2	6	6	5	-1	6	9	-5	7	1	6	-1	3	8	4	-2	4	4	5	6	2	6	2	2	6	4
7	6	-3	5	4	3	3	2	4	2	1	3	5	-3	8	-3	7	-1	1	6	7	-3	6	7	6	7	4	5	-1	-3	6	6
8	-1	-1	1	1	1	-2	1	2	2	-2	5	5	-5	6	-2	2	1	-4	1	2	-2	1	3	5	1	-2	1	2	2	5	7
9	4	3	2	3	1	3	2	-1	3	0	4	4	-1	4	-3	5	-1	-1	5	5	-3	4	5	2	3	3	6	3	-1	4	3
10	-2	-1	-1	-2	-1	-3	-1	3	-3	2	2	4	5	3	5	5	4	2	3	5	-5	3	4	3	3	1	2	4	3	-2	-2
11	1	1	-0	-1	1	-1	2	1	-1	4	3	7	-3	8	-1	7	3	2	7	6	-6	3	5	8	6	2	6	-1	2	3	4
12	5	-2	2	1	1	2	5	-1	2	3	4	2	-2	8	1	7	3	2	6	6	-8	3	7	9	7	-1	5	-1	2	5	5
13	2	-1	-0	-1	1	3	2	-2	2	-2	1	3	2	-5	2	-3	6	1	-5	-3	-3	-5	-4	-4	-4	-3	-5	-3	-3	-6	-8
14	6	2	4	5	2	4	6	-2	5	-4	-1	3	2	2	2	9	2	-1	8	9	-3	8	8	8	8	2	8	-1	1	4	5
15	-0	-0	-1	-2	-1	1	-1	-1	-1	1	-1	0	1	-1	1	4	3	2	2	4	1	5	4	4	3	-2	3	3	-6	3	2
16	4	-2	1	0	1	2	5	1	1	3	4	6	2	2	2	2	3	9	9	-5	8	9	9	10	-2	8	-1	-1	2	3	
17	1	-1	-1	-1	1	-1	2	-0	-1	1	2	2	1	-1	1	2	1	3	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	-5	1	-2	-1	-4	-2
18	-1	1	-2	-2	-0	0	-2	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	1	-1	1	-1	1	1	4	3	-6	-2	3	3	3	3	4	-2	-3	2	1
19	2	3	-1	2	-1	3	1	-3	4	-2	0	-1	1	4	1	1	-1	1	3	7	-5	5	7	7	9	1	9	-1	1	2	1
20	2	2	-1	1	-1	1	2	1	2	2	3	2	1	2	1	3	1	1	3	2	-4	9	10	8	9	4	9	1	-5	3	4
21	5	-1	2	2	2	3	3	-2	4	-5	-3	2	2	6	2	0	-0	-1	2	-1	1	1	-5	-6	-4	1	-3	3	2	-3	-2
22	-1	5	-2	1	-2	-0	-3	1	4	-1	1	-3	-1	3	-1	-1	-2	1	3	4	1	2	8	7	8	-2	7	1	-5	1	2
23	4	2	3	4	2	3	5	1	4	-2	3	3	1	6	-2	3	0	-1	3	4	3	4	1	9	8	3	7	1	-7	4	4
24	2	1	2	3	-1	0	4	2	3	2	2	2	-1	3	0	3	-1	-1	1	4	-1	4	4	2	9	2	8	2	-1	6	7
25	6	-2	5	4	3	3	8	1	3	-1	1	5	2	6	-1	5	1	-2	1	2	4	-2	6	4	2	3	9	2	-2	5	5
26	3	-1	2	1	2	3	3	1	2	2	2	4	3	3	-0	4	1	-1	1	2	2	-1	3	2	4	2	4	4	-4	6	6
27	1	1	-1	-2	-1	1	2	2	1	4	3	2	-1	-1	0	4	1	-1	3	4	-3	1	2	3	1	5	2	5	-2	6	6
28	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	-1	3	-2	-1	1	1	2	1	1	-1	-1	1	-1	2	1	2	1	2	1	-1	1	2	7	7
29	4	-1	3	3	2	3	3	-1	3	-3	-2	3	2	4	1	1	-1	-2	-1	-2	5	-2	3	-1	4	3	-3	3	1	-2	1
30	4	-2	3	2	3	2	4	1	2	-1	-1	3	1	3	-1	2	-1	-1	1	1	3	-2	3	2	4	4	1	2	3	2	10
31	-2	0	-1	-2	-1	-2	-2	3	0	3	0	-2	-3	-3	-0	1	-1	-1	-1	1	-2	2	-1	2	-2	2	3	1	-1	5	1

459 Numbers of traits are shown in Table 1. Significant correlations are marked in grey ($p < 0.05$), where: 0(≥ 0.00 and < 0.01),
 460 1(≥ 0.01 and < 0.10), 2(≥ 0.10 and < 0.20), 3(≥ 0.20 and < 0.30), 4(≥ 0.30 and < 0.40), 5(≥ 0.40 and < 0.50), 6(≥ 0.50 and < 0.60), 7(≥ 0.60
 461 and < 0.70), 8(≥ 0.70 and < 0.80), 9(≥ 0.80 and < 0.90) and 10(≥ 0.90 and < 1.00)
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